

2 **EFFECT OF THE START-STOP CYCLE OF CENTER-PIVOT**
3 **TOWERS ON IRRIGATION PERFORMANCE: EXPERIMENTS**
4 **AND SIMULATIONS**

5 Ouazaa, S.^(1.), Latorre, B.⁽²⁾, Burguete, J.⁽³⁾, Serreta, A.⁽⁴⁾, Playán, E.⁽⁵⁾, Salvador
6 R.⁽⁶⁾, Paniagua, P.⁽⁷⁾ and Zapata, N.^(8,*)

7 ^{(1).} Dept. Soil and Water. EEAD-CSIC. Avda. Montañana, 1005. 50059

8 Zaragoza. Spain. sofiane.ouazaa@eead.csic.es

9 ⁽²⁾ Dept. Soil and Water. EEAD-CSIC. Avda. Montañana, 1005. 50059

10 Zaragoza. Spain. borja.latorre@csic.es

11 ⁽³⁾ Dept. Soil and Water. EEAD-CSIC. Avda. Montañana, 1005. 50059

12 Zaragoza. Spain. jburguete@eead.csic.es

13 ⁽⁴⁾ Escuela Politécnica Superior, Universidad de Zaragoza, Ctra. Cuarte s/n,

14 22071 Huesca, Spain. serreta@unizar.es

15 ⁽⁵⁾ Dept. Soil and Water. EEAD-CSIC. Avda. Montañana, 1005. 50059

16 Zaragoza. Spain. enrique.playan@csic.es

17 ⁽⁶⁾ Dept. Soil and Water. EEAD-CSIC. Avda. Montañana, 1005. 50059

18 Zaragoza. Spain. rsalvador@eead.csic.es

19 ⁽⁷⁾ Dept. Soil and Water. EEAD-CSIC. Avda. Montañana, 1005. 50059

20 Zaragoza. Spain. pilucap@eead.csic.es

21 ^(8,*) Corresponding author. Dept. Soil and Water. EEAD-CSIC. Avda.

22 Montañana, 1005. 50059 Zaragoza. Spain. v.zapata@csic.es

24 **EFFECT OF THE START-STOP CYCLE OF CENTER-PIVOT**
25 **TOWERS ON IRRIGATION PERFORMANCE: EXPERIMENTS**
26 **AND SIMULATIONS**

27 **ABSTRACT**

28

29 The simulation of center-pivot performance has been the subject of research
30 efforts since the 1960s. Center-pivot models frequently use empirical equations
31 relating pressure and sprinkler radial application pattern. Individual, stationary
32 water application patterns are overlapped and the resulting water application is
33 mapped in the field. Such models use constant tower angular velocity,
34 neglecting the effect of tower alignment. In this work the discontinuous tower
35 movement has been experimentally characterized and modelled, and a
36 complete model has been developed by using a ballistic model of the center-
37 pivot sprinklers considering nozzle diameter, operating pressure and wind
38 speed. A detailed kinetic analysis of a four-tower commercial center-pivot was
39 performed. Each tower was monitored using a high precision GPS, recording
40 tower positions at high frequency. The experimental center-pivot was equipped
41 with fixed spray plate sprinklers (FSPS). Five experimental center-pivot
42 irrigation events were evaluated using catch-cans. The analysis of tower
43 location data permitted to conclude that two key variables (linear speed and
44 switching angle) showed normal distribution patterns. The center-pivot model
45 was validated with catch-can data. Finally, the simulation tool was used to
46 assess the effect of variable tower alignment quality, center-pivot travel speed
47 and wind conditions on irrigation performance. Comparisons were performed in

48 terms of radial, circular and total irrigation uniformity. Results indicate that the
49 observed tower dynamics had no measurable effect on irrigation uniformity.
50 Tower alignment quality started to be relevant when the switching angle lag was
51 equal to or larger than 5° . In the conditions of this analysis, wind speed showed
52 a clear effect on uniformity. As wind speed increased, uniformity first decreased
53 and then increased. Further research is required to generalize these results to
54 other center-pivot sizes and designs (sprinkler packages).

55

56 **I. INTRODUCTION**

57

58 Self-propelled sprinkler irrigation machines have experienced worldwide
59 success because of their advantages relative to other irrigation systems. Such
60 advantages typically include: 1) high potential for uniform and efficient water
61 application; 2) high degree of automation; and 3) ability to apply water and
62 nutrients over a wide range of soil, crop and topographic conditions (Evans and
63 King, 2012). For instance, self-propelled sprinkler irrigation machines irrigate
64 47% of the USA irrigated land, 20% of the Brazilian irrigated land and 8% of the
65 Spanish irrigated land.

66 Center-pivots can be driven by hydraulic or electric systems. Hydraulic systems
67 maintain all the towers in continuous motion, maintaining a perfect alignment.
68 Electric motion systems are the most common, owing to their simplicity and low
69 operating cost. In these systems the outermost tower is the master unit, driving
70 the rest of towers in response to angular displacement of the pipe section
71 adjacent thereto. The intermittent movement of each inner tower is dictated by
72 the alignment between two adjacent spans. The movement of the outermost
73 tower is governed by a percentage timer setting (PTS), which controls the ratio
74 between the irrigation system move time and the cycle time. The PTS value
75 also determines the irrigation depth resulting from a complete rotation, by
76 controlling the machine angular speed. The operator selects the PTS (or center-
77 pivot travel speed) in the central power control panel. At 100% PTS, the end
78 tower moves continuously. At 50% PTS, the end tower moves during half of the
79 cycle time. Consequently, at 50% PTS the applied irrigation depth doubles that

80 of 100% PTS. The most common cycle time of the end tower (considering
81 different center-pivot manufacturers) is 60 s.

82 Center-pivot irrigation uniformity is commonly evaluated by installing a radial
83 transect of catch cans extending outwards from the pivot point. This uniformity
84 measurement characterizes the functional performance of the sprinkler package
85 design and operation. Uniformity determined along the machine travel path is
86 assumed to be high because a continuous movement of the machine integrates
87 sprinkler pattern irregularities (Heermann and Kohl, 1980). However, tower
88 alignment can be poor. Additionally, at some towers large time lapses may
89 occur between moves (Hanson and Wallender, 1986). Since uniformity along
90 the travel path theoretically depends on the particular start/stop sequence, its
91 characterization will theoretically improve the simulation of the water distribution
92 pattern. Hanson and Wallender (1986) presented an experimental study to
93 analyse the effect of start/stop sequence on irrigation uniformity. They
94 concluded that non-uniformity along the travel path of a ten-tower center-pivot
95 appears in part related to the start/stop sequences of the towers. However, a
96 firm association was difficult to establish. Yan et al. (2010) presented another
97 experimental study analysing the effects of two center-pivot travel speeds and
98 two cycle times on irrigation performance, concluding that cycle time has a
99 slight effect on radial uniformity but no effect on circular uniformity.

100 The simulation of center-pivot water distribution patterns resulting from different
101 sprinkler types has traditionally been conducted by mathematically overlapping
102 experimentally measured isolated sprinkler patterns (Clark et al., 2003). Le Gat
103 and Molle (2000) proposed a model using a mixture of beta probability
104 distributions in which parameters were first estimated using water application

105 data measured in no-wind conditions. Data measured in wind conditions were
106 then used to assess wind effects on the water application patterns. Recently,
107 Sayyadi et al. (2012) proposed a new approach based on Artificial Neuronal
108 Networks (ANN) to simulate the effects of wind on the distribution pattern of
109 single sprinklers. The study presented the characterization of a unique nozzle
110 type and size, working at 140 kPa under different wind conditions. The
111 experimental effort necessary to train and validate the ANN model to simulate a
112 center-pivot package, with different nozzle sizes and working pressures, is time
113 and labour consuming.

114 An alternative approach to simulate the center-pivot water distribution pattern is
115 based on droplet trajectory modelling. The pressure head at the nozzle, the
116 nozzle diameter and the sprinkler design determine droplet size and velocity. In
117 kinetic energy analyses of sprinkler irrigation, droplet trajectory and velocity are
118 commonly simulated using an estimation of initial velocity and ballistic
119 simulation models (Kincaid, 1986). Ouazaa et al. (2013) presented the
120 characterization of initial velocity after the jet impact for FSPS equipped with a
121 36-grooved blue plate in an ample range of nozzle sizes and working at two
122 pressures (103 and 138 kPa, equivalent to 15 and 20 psi). The authors
123 presented the first application of the ballistic theory to the simulation of FSPS
124 water distribution pattern. Calibration and validation of the ballistic model
125 parameters were also presented for different nozzle sizes, wind conditions and
126 two working pressures.

127 The simulation of center-pivot performance has been addressed since the
128 1960s. Most of the developed models simplify irrigation machine dynamics
129 assuming continuous movement and circular sprinkler trajectory (Bittinger and

130 Logenbaugh, 1962; Heermann and Hein, 1968; Heermann and Stalk, 2004).
131 Omary and Sumner (2001) presented a model that only accounted for the
132 intermittent movement of the outermost tower, assuming perfect alignment
133 between all towers (hydraulic drive machine). Delirhasannia et al. (2010)
134 modified the model presented by Omary and Sumner (2001) to include the
135 effect of wind speed and direction on sprinkler water distribution patterns,
136 overlapping the experimental application patterns of isolated sprinklers.

137 The general objective of this paper is to develop a center-pivot simulation model
138 aiming at improving irrigation uniformity and at reducing water losses induced
139 by machine dynamics and wind speed. Specific objectives include:

- 140 1. To characterize and model the intermittent movement of center-pivot towers;
- 141 2. To couple the tower movement dynamics model with the ballistic simulation
142 of FSPS water distribution patterns;
- 143 3. To validate the coupled model with catch-can data; and
- 144 4. To analyse the effect of different tower movement dynamics, wind speeds
145 and center-pivot travel speeds on center-pivot irrigation system performance.

146

147 **II. MATERIAL AND METHODS**

148

149 Two field experiments were carried out to fulfil the specific objectives of this
150 research. In the first experiment, tower dynamics were characterized using a
151 commercial center-pivot. In the second experiment, five irrigation events of the
152 commercial center-pivot were evaluated with a catch-can radial transect. The
153 working pressure of the sprinkler package was also monitorized by installing ten
154 pressure transducers along the center-pivot lateral and another one at the
155 pumping station.

156 A scheme describing the interaction of the experimental work, the data analysis
157 and the model development is presented in Figure 1.

158

159 **II.1 Characterization of the center-pivot mechanical movement**

160

161 The first field experiment was conducted in a 16 ha commercial plot irrigated
162 with a center-pivot in Marracos (Huesca, Spain) during the 2012 irrigation
163 season. The center-pivot, a Valley machine (manufactured by Valmont
164 industries, Nebraska, USA), had four towers with 50 m spans and an overhang
165 of 25 m. The machine was equipped with Nelson D3000 (Nelson Irrigation Corp.
166 Walla Walla, Washington, USA) FSPS with 36-grooved blue plates and 138 kPa
167 (20 psi) pressure regulators. The center-pivot sprinkler package had 40 nozzles
168 of 21 different diameters ranging from 2.2 mm to 8.7 mm. The distance between
169 nozzles was constant and equal to 5.56 m. The first nozzle was installed at
170 10.27 m from the pivot point and the last one at 224.54 m from the pivot point.

171 Nozzles were located 2.0 m above the soil surface using a semi-rigid plastic
172 drop pipe.

173 The location of the four towers was tracked using high precision GPS receivers
174 (model GS15 receiver Leyca Geosystems AG, Heerbrugg, Switzerland)
175 installed on top of each tower (Figure 1a). Post processing of the recorded data
176 was performed to ensure positioning errors lower than 0.10 m. At the beginning
177 of the 2012 irrigation season the GPS receivers were programmed to log data
178 every 5 s. After five irrigation events, receivers were reprogrammed to log data
179 every second. The initial log frequency provided insufficient accuracy to
180 characterize tower movement. GPS data were used to characterize the
181 movement / stop cycle times in each tower and irrigation event. The time
182 evolution of the tower travel speed during the movement phase of each cycle
183 was obtained for each irrigation event. Fisher's Least Significant Difference
184 method (LSD) was used to compare tower travel speeds.

185 The on and off switching angle was determined for each tower and movement
186 cycle using the coordinates of the neighbouring towers. Tower acceleration and
187 deceleration times were also determined from experimental data. Acceleration
188 time (AT) was determined for each cycle as the time it takes for a tower to reach
189 its average travel speed. Deceleration time (DT) was determined as the time it
190 takes for a tower to stop from its average travel speed. Comparisons were
191 established for each center-pivot tower between AT and DT using paired-
192 sample t-test analyses. Statistical differences between towers were assessed
193 using the LSD test. The high number of movement / stop cycles within an
194 irrigation event evidenced inter- and intra-irrigation variability in tower travel
195 speed, switching angles, AT and DT.

196 Variability in tower travel speed and switching angles was explored in each
197 irrigation event using “interval method” frequency analysis. This method
198 consists on counting of the number of occurrences in previously defined
199 intervals. The number of movement / stop cycles per tower and irrigation event
200 was computed. Three irrigation events performed at 50%, 40% and 25% PTS
201 were selected to calibrate AT and DT via optimization. Five irrigation events
202 performed at 100%, 75%, 50%, 40% and 31% PTS were selected to validate
203 the center-pivot tower movement dynamic model (Figure 1e). This model
204 simulates center-pivots with tower motors similar to the experimental ones. The
205 outermost tower movement is driven by the percentage timer setting of the
206 correspondent center-pivot cycle time.

207

208 **II.2 Individual and stationary water distribution pattern of FSPS**

209 The parameters of the ballistic model applied to the simulation of FSPS were
210 obtained from Ouazza et al. (2013). These authors calibrated and validated
211 model parameters for 36-grooved, blue plate Nelson D3000 FSPS for a range
212 of nozzle diameters from 2.4 to 8.7 mm, working at pressures in the range of
213 103 to 138 kPa (15 to 20 psi) and under different wind conditions (from 0 to 8m
214 s⁻¹). The resulting ballistic model was used to simulate the water application
215 pattern corresponding to the different nozzle sizes of the commercial center-
216 pivot package, operating at the design pressure and at the meteorological
217 conditions of the evaluated irrigation events.

218

219 **II.3 Catch-can evaluation**

220 Five irrigation events were evaluated with catch-cans arranged in a radial
221 transect line with a 2 m spacing (Fig. 1 b). A total of 24 catch-cans were
222 installed per pivot span, except for the first span, which was not monitored. Only
223 13 catch-cans were installed at the center-pivot overhang. Catch cans were
224 conical in its lower part (200 mm height) and cylindrical in its upper part (100
225 mm height); the diameter of the upper part was 160 mm. The catch cans were
226 marked in millimetres for direct readout up to 45 mm. They were placed over
227 mowed corn at approximately 1.0 m above the ground.

228 An automatic meteorological station located adjacent to the center-pivot plot
229 (Fig. 1b) monitored wind velocity and direction, air temperature and relative
230 humidity with a frequency of 1 s. A 3-cup rotor anemometer Series A-100 and a
231 wind direction sensor model 024-L (Campbell Scientific Ltd., Shepshed, UK)
232 were used to measure wind speed and direction, respectively. A model CS-215
233 probe (Campbell Scientific Ltd., Shepshed, UK) was used to measure
234 temperature and relative humidity. Meteorological variables were recorded in a
235 model CR1000 data-logger (Campbell Scientific Ltd, Shepshed, UK).

236 To characterize the meteorological conditions of the evaluated irrigation events,
237 GPS data of the center-pivot towers were analysed to estimate the passing time
238 period of the center-pivot lateral over the radial catch-can transect. The vector
239 average of wind velocity and direction, the average temperature and the
240 average relative humidity of the selected irrigation period were considered
241 representative of the evaluated irrigation. Eleven pressure transducers-loggers
242 (Dixon, model PR150) were installed, one at the pumping station and the others
243 along the center-pivot lateral (Figure 1b). Pressure transducers provided
244 measurements with a 5 min time interval. The first measurement point at the

245 irrigation lateral was located at the pivot point (maximum elevation). The other
246 nine pressure transducers were installed at the drop pipes, between the
247 pressure regulator (138 kPa) and the sprinkler nozzle. Two pressure
248 transducers per span were installed: one at the first nozzle and the other at the
249 nozzle located in the middle of the span. The last transducer was installed at
250 the beginning of the overhang. The average of the two pressure transducer
251 measurements of a given span at the passing time of the center-pivot lateral
252 over the radial catch can transect was used as representative of the span
253 nozzle pressure.

254

255 **II.4 Validation and application of the simulation model coupling tower** 256 **dynamics and sprinkler water distribution patterns**

257

258 The water distribution patterns for the different nozzle diameters of the center-
259 pivot sprinkler package were simulated following Ouazaa et al. (2013).
260 Simulations were performed under the different wind conditions and at the
261 measured working pressure of the evaluated irrigation events. Each simulation
262 involved mounting the water distribution patterns under the four spans and the
263 overhang, and intermittently moving them with the pivot towers following the
264 current measured dynamics (Fig. 1f). Model validation involved comparing
265 simulated and measured (catch can evaluation data) irrigation depths and
266 irrigation uniformities. Model application permitted to assess the effect of the
267 PTS on the irrigation uniformity for different wind speed conditions and under
268 different alignment qualities. Three PTS (30%, 50% and 100%), three wind
269 conditions (three of the evaluated irrigation events) and four alignment qualities

270 were simulated. The analysed alignment qualities addressed the effect of the
 271 towers' start/stop sequences on irrigation performance. Comparisons were
 272 established between a center-pivot traveling under complete alignment
 273 (Complete), a center-pivot incorporating the current tower dynamics (CD), a
 274 center-pivot with a difference between on and off switching angles of 1° (A 1°)
 275 and a center-pivot with a difference between on and off switching angles of 2°
 276 (A 2°).

277 Each simulated irrigation event considered constant wind speed, wind direction,
 278 and pressure during the irrigation time. Comparisons between simulated cases
 279 were established in terms of radial, circular and total uniformity. Eight radial
 280 transects starting from the East (R-0°), separated 45° and following a counter
 281 clockwise direction were selected to estimate radial uniformity (along the
 282 lateral). Nine circular paths, corresponding to distances of 20, 40, 70, 90, 120,
 283 140, 170, 190 and 220 m from the pivot point, were selected to estimate circular
 284 uniformity (along the machine travel path). Additionally, a total uniformity
 285 coefficient corresponding to the entire irrigated field was determined. The
 286 Heermann and Hein uniformity coefficient (CU_{HH} , %) (Equation [2]) was used for
 287 irrigation performance characterization of measured and simulated radial
 288 application data (Heermann and Hein, 1968).

$$289 \quad CU_{HH} = 100 * \left[1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^m |d_i - \bar{d}_w| * S_i}{\sum_{i=1}^m d_i * S_i} \right] \quad [2]$$

290 where S_i is the distance from the pivot point to the i_{th} collector, d_i is the collected
 291 water depth in the i_{th} collector, m is the number of collectors, and \bar{d}_w is the
 292 weighted average of collected water amounts (Equation [3]):

293
$$\bar{d}_w = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{i=m} d_i * S_i}{\sum_{i=1}^{i=m} S_i} \quad [3]$$

294 The Christiansen Uniformity Coefficient (CUC, %) (Equation [4]) was used for
 295 the simulated circular paths and for the total irrigated area:

296
$$CUC = 100 * \left[1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{i=m} |d_i - \bar{d}|}{\bar{d} * m} \right] \quad [4]$$

297

298 **III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**

299

300 **III.1 Characterizing and modelling center-pivot dynamics**

301

302 The experimental center-pivot applied 59 irrigation events, completing 70.4
 303 rounds in 1,472.4 hours throughout the 2012 irrigation season. A total of 50 of
 304 these irrigations had sufficient data quality to be used to characterize center-
 305 pivot movement. The selected irrigations completed 50.2 rounds in 1,182.8
 306 hours. These irrigation events used a variety of PTS, with 35% and 50% being
 307 the most frequent (80% of the irrigation events and 64.5% of the irrigated
 308 hours). The average cycle time for the outermost tower was 71.6 s, with an
 309 inter-irrigation standard deviation of 0.4 s. This cycle time slightly differs from
 310 the most commonly used by center-pivot manufacturers.

311 The farmer uses the water application chart provided by the manufacturer to
 312 operate the center-pivot. This chart specifies that at 100% PTS the revolution
 313 time is 9.5 hours and the theoretical irrigation depth is 4.1 mm. At different PTS
 314 the revolution time and the irrigation depth can be obtained by dividing values

315 above by the value of PTS. Figure 2 presents the comparison between the
316 measured and manufacturer-provided relationships between PTS and irrigation
317 time. A regression analysis between measured and manufacturer-provided
318 irrigation time showed that the correlation coefficient was not statistically
319 different from 1. These results indicate that the experimental center-pivot
320 movement is as originally manufactured.

321 Table 1 summarizes the results for the main tower dynamics variables. Some of
322 these variables were used for simulation parameterization purposes. Measured
323 average and inter-irrigation standard deviation tower travel speed were obtained
324 from 45 analysed irrigation events (Table 1). Fisher's Least Significant
325 Difference (LSD) method indicated that T4 speed was significantly different from
326 the inner tower (T1, T2 and T3) speeds (95% confidence level). The test also
327 indicated that T1, T2 and T3 speeds were statistically similar. The motors of the
328 four towers had the same characteristics. Consequently, differences in speed
329 can only be attributed to differences in load and/or to differences in tensions
330 from the adjacent towers. The travel speed of the three inner towers was 80%
331 of the speed of the outermost tower. The average inter-irrigation standard
332 deviation of tower travel speed resulted very low (Table 1).

333 Comparison between AT and DT for each tower (t-test) showed significant
334 differences except for T1. However, the differences in T2, T3 and T4 (average
335 of 0.12 s) were lower than the measurement interval (1 s). Comparisons
336 between towers (LSD test) indicated that the ATs of T2, T3 and T4 were not
337 statistically different. However, they were found to be statistically different from
338 the DT of T2, T3 and T4. Again the magnitude of the differences was lower than
339 the measurement interval.

340 The intra-irrigation variability of towers' travel speed was evaluated using a
341 frequency analysis. These travel speed analyses were performed only for the
342 movement part of the cycles. Four irrigation events performed at different PTS
343 (75%, 50%, 40% and 25%) were selected (Figure 3). For a given irrigation
344 event the tower travel speed presented a clear distribution pattern, which was
345 similar for irrigations performed at different PTS. For each tower, the intra-
346 irrigation variability (amplitude of the histogram) was larger than the inter-
347 irrigation variability (difference between histograms). Intra-irrigation variability
348 increased from the inner tower (T1) to the outermost tower (T4). Figure 3 also
349 shows relevant similarities between the inner towers' (T1, T2 and T3) travel
350 speed patterns, and the difference with the outermost tower travel speed
351 pattern (T4).

352 Figure 4 presents the frequency analysis of the on and off switching angles
353 controlling the movement / stop cycles of towers T1, T2 and T3 for four irrigation
354 events performed at 75 %, 50 %, 40 % and 25 % PTS. The T1 on and off
355 switching angles computed with the locations of the pivot point (T0), T1 and T2
356 did not show a clear variability pattern. Their behaviour was very different from
357 T2 and T3, and the error was attributed to the determination of T0 co-ordinates.
358 Since T0 was a fixed point a GPS receiver was not permanently installed at this
359 point. T0 location was measured once after the season, and the satellite
360 positioning correction was applied at that moment. On the other hand, the GPS
361 records from T1, T2, T3 and T4 were continuously corrected through satellite
362 positioning. Differences in the measurement and correction times resulted in
363 relevant errors affecting T1 angles.

364 The distribution pattern for the T2 and T3 switching angles was similar for
365 irrigations performed at different PTS. The average measured on switch angles
366 for T2 and T3 were 179.7° and 179.5° , respectively. An average value of nearly
367 180.0° was found for the off switch angle corresponding to T2 and T3 (Table 1).
368 Again, the intra-irrigation variability (the amplitude of the histograms) was larger
369 than the inter-irrigation variability (differences between histograms). An intra-
370 irrigation standard deviation of 0.0655° was found for all the measured
371 switching angles.

372 A simulation model of tower movement was proposed based on the analysis of
373 the experimental data. The model simulates a center-pivot with similar individual
374 motors powering the wheels of each tower. The outside tower advances
375 following the pre-set PTS. Inner tower dynamics are driven by the on and off
376 switching angles, for which a restricted random variability was built, reproducing
377 the experimental variability.

378 Linear speeds and control angles were obtained for each tower from Table 1 to
379 simulate the current center-pivot dynamics. The switching angles were
380 considered equal for all inner towers (Table 1). To simulate the intra-irrigation
381 variability of the switching angles, a random value between 0 and the observed
382 variability (0.0655°) was added to the average values.

383 Instead of using the average values of the experimentally determined AT and
384 DT, the Monte Carlo simulation method (Fishman, 1995) was used to optimize
385 their values. The goal was to analyse the effect of the AT and DT on the
386 simulation of the center-pivot tower dynamics. The objective function for the
387 Monte Carlo method was based on the minimization of two errors: 1) the total
388 movement and stop times for each tower; and 2) the distribution frequency of

389 the movement and stop times for each of the towers. Three irrigation events
390 performed under different PTS (50%, 40% and 25%) were used for optimization
391 purposes. The Monte Carlo process provided an optimized value of 2.45 s for
392 both, AT and DT. Table 1 presents the input data for the simulation model.

393 Model validation used the same cycle time as measured (71.6 s). Five part-
394 circle (180°) irrigation events performed at different PTS (100%, 75%, 50%,
395 40% and 31%) were selected for validation purposes. For these irrigation
396 events a detailed analysis of the experimental data was performed, and
397 observations were compared to simulation results. Table 2 presents the
398 comparison for total movement time and total stop time for each tower and
399 irrigation event. In general, simulated times were slightly larger than measured
400 times. However, differences were always lower than 4.2% of the measured
401 times.

402 In addition, the model should also adequately simulate the movement and stop
403 cycle times for each tower. Figures 5 and 6 present measured and simulated
404 frequency analyses of the on-times (left side figures) and off-times (right side
405 figures) for each tower and for the validation irrigation events performed at 40%
406 and 75% PTS, respectively. The measured variability of the movement and stop
407 cycle times was in general well reproduced by the model. It has to be noted that
408 the frequency analysis used a 5 s time step. An important difference in the
409 specific duration will not be so important if it is compensated by the immediately
410 previous or subsequent cycle time. For example, this is the case for the
411 movement cycle time of tower 4 for the irrigation performed at 40% PTS (bottom
412 left Figure 5). Measured movement cycle durations ranged between 25-30 s
413 and between 30-35 s, with respective frequencies of 452 and 110 events. The

414 simulated cycle durations of 25-30 s had a frequency of 574 events. Although
415 the difference appears graphically important, its effect on machine movement is
416 not relevant.

417 **III.2 Irrigation evaluation results**

418 Table 3 summarizes the results of the evaluated irrigation events. Results are
419 presented for each evaluated center-pivot span. For the first and second
420 irrigation events all the center-pivot length was measured (Fig. 1b). After the
421 second evaluated irrigation event it was necessary to uninstall the catch-can
422 radial transect for agronomical operations. It was decided to reinstall catch-cans
423 only under the fourth span, and occasionally under the overhang.
424 Consequently, for the third irrigation event only the catch cans of the fourth
425 span and the overhang were measured; for the fourth and fifth irrigation events
426 only the fourth span was measured.

427 The average pressure at the pumping station (all the evaluated irrigation
428 events) was 218 kPa, with a standard deviation between irrigations of 4.5 kPa.
429 The average pressure measured at the center-pivot point was of 140 kPa, with
430 a standard deviation between irrigations of 5.0 kPa. Although all the nozzles
431 were equipped with a pressure regulator of 138 kPa, slight differences in
432 working pressure were measured along the center-pivot lateral (Table 3). From
433 the first span to the middle of the fourth span, the operating pressure could be
434 considered similar to the regulator setting. Pressure at the beginning of the
435 overhang measurement point was lower than the regulator setting in all
436 evaluated irrigation events. A pressure of 138 kPa was used to simulate the
437 nozzles located at the first, second, third and fourth span. A pressure of 130kPa
438 was used at the nozzles located at the overhang.

439 The measured CU_{HH} was affected by wind speed and the sprinkler package
440 (Table 3). Comparing the CU_{HH} of the fourth span in different irrigation events, a
441 decrease in uniformity was observed from low (1.1 m s^{-1}) to medium (2.8 m s^{-1})
442 wind speeds. Uniformity increased in this span from medium (3.1 m s^{-1}) to high
443 wind speeds (4.7 and 4.9 m s^{-1}). Irrigation events 2 and 3 were performed under
444 similar average wind conditions, but CU_{HH} at the fourth span resulted different.
445 Uniformity can be dictated not only by the average wind conditions, but also by
446 the short-term wind variability in intensity and direction. Additionally, Faci et al.
447 (2001) and Ouazaa et al. (2013) underlined the difficulty of experimentally
448 characterizing water distribution patterns of FSPS using catch-cans.

449

450 **III.3 A model coupling tower dynamics and water application patterns:** 451 **validation and application**

452

453 The spatial water application to the irrigated area was computed using a static
454 grid whose parameters can be user-defined. The static grid is irrigated by
455 moving grids representing the water distribution pattern of the sprinklers along
456 the center-pivot lateral. The grids representing the sprinklers were computed
457 using ballistic theory as reported in Ouazza et al. (2013). Other authors have
458 used experimentally determined water distribution grids (Delirhasannia et al,
459 2010) or statistically defined water distribution patterns (Gat and Molle, 2000).
460 The advantage of the method used in this paper is that model parameters can
461 be extrapolated to non-evaluated nozzle diameters (within the experimental
462 range), wind speeds (from 0 to 8 m s^{-1}) and working pressures (from 15 to 20
463 psi).

464 The effect of grid size on center-pivot irrigation performance was analysed. Five
465 square grid sizes (from 0.5 m to 0.03125 m in side) defining the nozzle water
466 distribution pattern of each sprinkler were simulated with the ballistic model
467 presented in Ouazaa et al (2013). Relevant differences in distribution uniformity
468 were observed between the simulated results with the coarse grid (0.5 m) and
469 the fine grid (0.03125 m). Since differences between the two fine grids (0.0625
470 m and 0.03125 m) were negligible, the 0.0625 m grid was selected to represent
471 the sprinkler water application pattern.

472 The five evaluated irrigation events were simulated to validate the model. The
473 simulated nozzle patterns (under variable diameter, pressure and wind) were
474 mounted at their corresponding locations. Center-pivot movement was
475 simulated using the experimental parameters (PTS of 45% for irrigation events
476 1 and 5, and PTS of 50% for irrigation events 2, 3 and 4). Irrigation depths were
477 simulated at the location of the experimental catch-cans.

478 Figure 7a presents the relationship between measured and simulated irrigation
479 depth of the evaluated events (as presented in Table 3). The 1:1 line is
480 presented in dashed line. The comparison regression line forced to the origin
481 between measured and simulated irrigation depths has a slope of 1.0007 and is
482 not statistically different from 1. The ballistic model presented in Ouazaa et al.
483 (2013) included the experimental wind drift and evaporation losses (WDEL)
484 function presented in Playan et al. (2005). These authors reported experimental
485 WDEL in sprinkler irrigation machines of around 10% for daytime irrigation
486 events. Figure 7b presents the comparison between measured and simulated
487 CU_{HH} . The regression line forced to the origin has a slope of 1.005. This line is
488 not statistically different from the 1:1 line (dashed line in Fig. 7b). The coupled

489 simulation model adequately reproduces irrigation depth and irrigation
490 performance (CU_{HH}).

491 Different center-pivot sprinkler package designs (nozzle location and sizing),
492 dynamics (PTS and alignments) and meteorological conditions (wind speed and
493 direction) can be simulated with the developed model. In this study four
494 scenarios of the experimental center-pivot tower dynamics (Complete, CD, A 1°
495 and A 2°) were explored using the experimental sprinkler package. These
496 alternative dynamics were simulated for three PTS (100%, 50% and 30%) and
497 three wind speed conditions (1.1 m s^{-1} , 3.1 m s^{-1} and 4.7 m s^{-1}). Results were
498 compared in terms of radial (R-), circular (C-) and total uniformity.

499 Average radial, circular and total irrigation depths (ID, mm) and uniformities
500 (CU_{HH} and CUC, %) for the three PTS, the four alignment scenarios and the
501 three wind speed conditions are summarized in Table 4. As expected, simulated
502 average irrigation depth increases with PTS (from 4.1 for 100% to 13.5 for
503 30%). These values are similar to those provided by the manufacturer in the
504 experimental center-pivot application chart. A comparison between simulated
505 and manufacturer-provided ID is presented in Figure 2.

506 The effect of center-pivot travel speed (PTS, %) on CU (radial, circular or total)
507 was in general irrelevant, except for the cases of the largest misalignment (A
508 2°), in which for the slowest PTS (30%) radial CU_{HH} increased respect to the
509 fastest PTS (100%) (from 0.8 to 1.8 percent points). The effect of PTS was
510 lowest for the circular and total uniformity coefficients.

511 In the experimental center-pivot and environmental conditions, the effect of the
512 studied range of tower alignment qualities on irrigation uniformity can be
513 classified as light. Radial, circular and total uniformity slightly decrease as

514 misalignment increases. This issue will require further analysis for different pivot
515 lengths and sprinkler characteristics.

516 Wind speed effect on irrigation uniformity shows the same pattern for the radial,
517 circular and total uniformity. However, the effect is clearer for circular uniformity
518 than for the rest of parameters. From low to average wind speed (from 1.1 to
519 3.1 m s^{-1}), the average decrease in uniformity is 5.3%, 0.5% and 0.4% for
520 circular, radial and total uniformity, respectively. On the other hand, from
521 medium to strong wind speeds (from 3.1 to 4.7 m s^{-1}) the average increase in
522 uniformity is 7.3%, 3% and 3.1%, for circular, radial and total uniformity,
523 respectively. It has to be noted that real center-pivot irrigation event last for
524 several hours, and meteorological conditions (such as wind speed and
525 direction) may show relevant changes. This important effect has not been
526 analysed in this study. The small effect of alignment quality and PTS on
527 uniformity increases with wind speed.

528 The center-pivot dynamic model permits to explore the maximum misalignment
529 between adjacent towers that a defined center-pivot can allow before collapse.
530 Center-pivot tower travel speed and reach length determine the maximum
531 allowed misalignment. For the studied commercial center-pivot, the maximum
532 misalignment between towers was 15° . Larger values could not be managed by
533 the current towers' speeds and the security system of the center-pivot would
534 stop movement.

535 A further analysis of tower alignment quality on center-pivot irrigation
536 performance is presented in Figure 8. The Figure includes radial, circular and
537 total uniformities and their variability (standard deviation of the eight radial
538 transects and nine circular paths) for the center-pivot traveling under five

539 alignment scenarios: Complete, CD, A 5°, A 10° and A 15°. Simulations were
540 performed for 100% PTS under three wind speed conditions (1.1 m s⁻¹,
541 3.1 m s⁻¹ and 4.7 m s⁻¹, subfigures a, b and c, respectively). For low and strong
542 winds (1.1 and 4.7 m s⁻¹) circular uniformities were considerably larger than
543 radial and total uniformities. Differences between extreme misalignment
544 qualities on circular uniformity were larger (from 6.7 to 9%) than radial (from 2.8
545 to 4.8%) and total (2.8 to 5.3%) uniformities. Also, the variability in circular
546 uniformity was significantly larger than in radial uniformity. The variability in
547 radial uniformity increased with misalignment and with wind speed. The
548 variability in circular uniformities increased from low to average wind speed and
549 then decreased for strong wind speeds. In general, radial uniformity provides a
550 better approximation to total uniformity than circular uniformity. Center-pivot
551 evaluation standards (UNE-EN ISO 11545:2002 and ANSI/ASAE S436.1) are
552 only based on radial uniformity characterization. For average wind speeds the
553 radial, circular and total uniformities were found to be quite similar (Figure 8b).
554 Generalizing, tower misalignment reduces irrigation performance (radial,
555 circular and total). The reduction starts to be relevant for misalignment larger
556 than A 5°. Figure 9 provides a visual representation of simulated water
557 distributions resulting from three alignment qualities: Complete (Figure 9a), A 5°
558 (Figure 9b) and A 15° (Figure 9c). Simulations were performed under 3.1 m s⁻¹
559 wind speed at 100% PTS. The towers stop and start cycles result in different
560 amounts of local water application, the effect is stronger for the largest
561 misalignment analysed and for the area irrigated by the inner towers.
562 Differences in radial, circular and total uniformity between the Complete and A
563 5° alignment qualities were 1.1%, 1.2% and 1.2%, respectively. Differences in

564 radial, circular and total uniformity between the two extreme alignment qualities
565 (Complete and A 15°) were 4.8%, 7.0% and 5.3%, respectively.

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CONCLUSIONS

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569 1. The experimental characterization of the mechanical movement of center-
570 pivot towers using a high precision GPS receiver provided valuable
571 information to develop a comprehensive center-pivot irrigation simulation
572 model. A position sampling interval of 1 s was required to guarantee
573 sufficient accuracy in the characterization of tower movement. An
574 important intra-irrigation variability of the variables controlling tower start /
575 stop cycles was observed. This variability was modelled by introducing
576 random variability in the switching angles. The proposed model
577 successfully simulated the mechanical movement of the center-pivot
578 towers.

579 2. The simulation model coupling center-pivot tower dynamics and the FSPS
580 water distribution pattern satisfactorily reproduced the measured center-
581 pivot irrigation depth and radial uniformity.

582 3. The coupled model was used to analyse the effect of different tower
583 alignment qualities and wind speeds on the radial (along lateral), circular
584 (along machine travel path) and total water uniformity. Simulation results
585 indicate that in the experimental conditions (four span pivot, FSPS, wind
586 speed) the experimentally measured tower alignment quality (around 0.5°)
587 did not have a relevant effect on uniformity compared to a complete

588 alignment. The poorest analysed tower alignment quality (A 15°) had more
589 effect on circular uniformity than on radial or total uniformity.

590 4. In the experimental conditions and in the simulated range of the control
591 variables, tower alignment quality showed a relevant effect on center-pivot
592 irrigation performance for misalignment qualities larger than 5°. Pivot travel
593 speed showed a mild effect on center-pivot irrigation performance. The
594 sprinkler package design of the center-pivot had a strong effect on
595 irrigation performance.

596 5. Wind speed showed a clear effect on irrigation uniformity. As wind speed
597 increased, uniformity first decreased and then increased. The wind speed
598 effect is clearer for circular uniformity than for radial or total uniformity.

599 6. Further research is needed to assess the effect of alignment, travel speed
600 and wind conditions on other center-pivot lengths, sprinklers and
601 operational conditions. The simulation of the intra-irrigation variability of
602 wind speed seems to be important to understand center-pivot irrigation
603 efficiency.

604 7. The model shows potential to become a valuable tool to manage center-
605 pivot irrigation under different technical and meteorological conditions.
606 Further research on sprinklers and designs will contribute to validate the
607 practical potential of this coupled model.

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GLOSSARY OF ABBREVIATIONS

621 A 1° = Center-pivot dynamics with a difference between on and of switching

622 angles of 1°;

623 A 2° = Center-pivot dynamics with a difference between on and of switching

624 angles of 2°;

625 A 5° = Center-pivot dynamics with a difference between on and of switching

626 angles of 5°;

627 A 10° = Center-pivot dynamics with a difference between on and of switching

628 angles of 10°;

629 A 15° = Center-pivot dynamics with a difference between on and of switching

630 angles of 15°;

631 Complete = Center-pivot dynamics complete aligned;

632 AT = Acceleration time (s);

633 C = Circular;

634 CD = Center-pivot movement with the current experimental dynamics;

635 CUC = Christiansen Uniformity Coefficient (%);

636 CU_{HH} = Herman and Hein Uniformity Coefficient (%);

637 d = Average collected water depth (mm);

638 d_i = Water depth collected in the i_{th} collector (mm);

639 DT = Deceleration time (s);

640 d_w = Weighted average of collected water depths (mm);

641 FSPS = Fixed Spray Plate Sprinkler;

642 GPS = Global Position System;

643 ID = Irrigation depth (mm);

- 644 LSD = Fisher's least significant difference test;
- 645 m = Number of collector;
- 646 PTS = Percent Timer Setting (%);
- 647 R = Radial;
- 648 S_i = Distance from the center-pivot point to the i_{th} collector (m);
- 649 T1= Inner tower of the experimental center-pivot;
- 650 T2= Second center-pivot tower from the pivot point;
- 651 T3= Third center-pivot tower from the pivot point;
- 652 T4= Outermost tower of the experimental centre-pivot;
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723 50% and 30%).

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730 Figure 1. Scheme describing the research methodology. The set-up of the field
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732 tower dynamics and b) Center-pivot irrigation evaluations by catch can
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759 3.3 m s^{-1} and 4.7 m s^{-1}) for the commercial center-pivot traveling at 100% PTS.

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762 and at its maximum tower misalignment (A 15° , figure c) at 100% PTS and at
763 a wind speed of 3.3 m s^{-1} .

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 766 Table 1. Average values of tower travel speed (with standard deviation in
 767 brackets), on switch angle, off switch angle, standard deviation of the intra-
 768 irrigation switch angles and Acceleration / Deceleration Time (AT / DT) for
 769 each pivot tower. Measured values and simulation input values are presented.

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	Tower	Tower speed (m s ⁻¹)	AT/DT (s)	On switch angle (°)	Off switch angle (°)	SD Switching angles (°)
Measured	T1	0.0302 (0.003)	2.8/2.8	-	-	-
	T2	0.0302 (0.004)	2.7/2.8	179.7	180.0	0.0655
	T3	0.0303 (0.003)	2.7/3.0	179.5	180.0	0.0655
	T4	0.0377 (0.003)	2.7/2.9	-	-	-
Simulated experimental dynamics	T1	0.0302	2.45	179.6	180.0	0.0655
	T2	0.0302	2.45	179.6	180.0	0.0655
	T3	0.0302	2.45	179.6	180.0	0.0655
	T4	0.0377	2.45	-	-	-

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786 Table 2. Measured and simulated total movement and stop time for the four
 787 pivot towers and for five irrigation events performed at different PTS (31%,
 788 40%, 50%, 75% and 100%). Differences between measured and simulated
 789 times are presented.

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Timer Setting	Tower	Measured		Simulated		Δ (Measured-Simulated)	
		Movement Time (s)	Stop Time (s)	Movement Time (s)	Stop Time (s)	Movement Time (s)	Stop Time (s)
100%	T1	5080	11329	5204	11500	-124	-171
	T2	10198	6216	10407	6296	-209	-80
	T3	15260	1127	15607	1096	-347	31
	T4	16423	0	16703	0	-280	0
75%	T1	5124	17214	5202	16989	-78	225
	T2	10277	12056	10404	11787	-127	269
	T3	15451	6868	15613	6578	-162	290
	T4	16794	5514	16704	5487	90	27
50%	T1	5118	27608	5198	27942	-80	-334
	T2	10238	22546	10403	22737	-165	-191
	T3	15482	17286	15606	17534	-124	-248
	T4	16496	16263	16704	16437	-208	-174
40%	T1	5168	35622	5199	35800	-31	-178
	T2	10292	30496	10396	30603	-104	-107
	T3	15451	25342	15595	25404	-144	-62
	T4	16620	24204	16703	24295	-83	-91
31%	T1	5118	47964	5191	48315	-73	-351
	T2	10230	42853	10389	43116	-159	-263
	T3	15446	37681	15593	37912	-147	-231
	T4	16554	36566	16703	36803	-149	-237

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801 Table 3. Characteristics of the evaluated irrigation event, center-pivot travel
 802 speed (PTS, %), average wind speed, predominant wind direction, catch can
 803 location, average pressure at the span, average measured irrigation depth (ID,
 804 mm), standard deviation of the irrigation depth (SD ID, mm) and measured
 805 radial uniformities (CU_{HH} , %).
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Irrigation event	PTS (%)	Av. Wind Speed ($m s^{-1}$)	Av. Wind Direction ($^{\circ}$)	Catch can Location*	Av. Pressure (kPa)**	Measured		
						ID (mm)	SD ID (mm)	CU_{HH} (%)
Event 1	45	3.1	278	Span 2 (24)	142 (3)	7.8	1.6	83.5
Event 1	45	3.1	278	Span 3 (24)	138 (3)	8.5	2.2	77.4
Event 1	45	3.1	278	Span 4 (24)	136 (5)	8.5	2.0	80.9
Event 1	45	3.1	278	Overhang (13)	130 (9)	8.3	2.6	74.4
Event 2	50	4.7	273	Span 2 (24)	142 (3)	7.0	1.2	87.0
Event 2	50	4.7	273	Span 3 (24)	139 (4)	7.5	1.0	86.3
Event 2	50	4.7	273	Span 4 (24)	135 (4)	7.0	1.3	86.8
Event 2	50	4.7	273	Overhang (13)	130 (6)	6.4	1.6	77.9
Event 3	50	4.9	275	Span 4 (24)	136 (5)	6.4	1.3	83.3
Event 3	50	4.9	275	Overhang (13)	130 (5)	7.0	2.0	78.5
Event 4	50	2.8	271	Span 4 (24)	136 (5)	7.8	1.9	79.0
Event 5	45	1.1	250	Span 4 (24)	136 (5)	8.5	1.8	82.5

807 *Number of catch-cans between brackets

808 **Standard deviation between brackets

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827 Table 4. Simulated radial, circular and total, average irrigation depth (Av. ID, mm) and uniformity coefficient (CU, %) for four
828 analysed tower alignment scenarios: Complete aligned, current dynamics, and alternative dynamics allowing angle lags of 1° (A
829 1°) and 2° (A 2°) and for the three wind speeds (1.1 m s⁻¹, 3.3 m s⁻¹ and 4.7 m s⁻¹). Results are presented for three PTS (100%,
830 50% and 30%).

Wind Speed	Measurement Location	Align. Quality PTS (%)	Complete Aligned			Current Dynamics			A 1°			A 2°		
			100	50	30	100	50	30	100	50	30	100	50	30
1.1 m s ⁻¹	Radial	Av ID (mm)	4.1	8.0	13.1	4.1	8.1	13.5	4.1	8.1	13.5	4.2	8.1	13.5
		CU _{HH} (%)	81.6	81.6	81.5	81.7	81.6	81.6	81.3	81.4	81.5	80.8	81.6	81.6
	Circular	Av ID (mm)	3.8	7.4	12.1	3.7	7.4	12.4	3.7	7.4	12.4	3.7	7.4	12.4
		CUC (%)	86.2	86.1	86.1	86.1	86.1	86.1	85.9	86.0	86.0	85.5	85.2	86.1
	TOTAL	Av ID (mm)	4.1	8.0	13.1	4.0	8.1	13.5	4.1	8.1	13.5	4.0	8.1	13.5
		CUC (%)	82.1	82.1	82.1	82.1	82.1	82.1	82.0	82.0	82.0	81.7	81.7	81.8
3.1 m s ⁻¹	Radial	Av ID (mm)	4.1	8.0	13.0	4.1	8.1	13.6	4.1	8.1	13.6	4.2	8.0	13.6
		CU _{HH} (%)	81.2	81.2	81.3	81.0	81.3	81.0	80.6	81.0	81.3	80.0	80.3	81.8
	Circular	Av ID (mm)	4.0	8.0	13.0	4.0	8.0	13.4	4.0	8.1	13.4	4.0	8.1	13.4
		CUC (%)	80.8	80.8	80.8	80.8	80.7	80.7	80.7	80.8	80.7	80.1	80.3	80.3
	TOTAL	Av ID (mm)	4.1	8.0	13.1	4.1	8.1	13.5	4.1	8.1	13.5	4.1	8.1	13.5
		CUC (%)	81.7	81.7	81.7	81.7	81.7	81.7	81.6	81.7	81.7	81.3	81.3	81.4
4.7 m s ⁻¹	Radial	Av ID (mm)	4.1	8.0	13.1	4.1	8.1	13.5	4.1	8.1	13.6	4.2	8.0	11.6
		CU _{HH} (%)	84.3	84.3	84.2	84.1	84.2	84.1	83.7	84.1	84.3	82.9	83.0	84.8
	Circular	Av ID (mm)	4.1	8.1	13.2	4.1	8.2	13.6	4.1	8.2	13.6	4.1	8.2	13.6
		CUC (%)	88.1	88.1	88.1	88.1	88.1	88.1	88.0	88.1	88.0	87.0	87.3	87.7
	TOTAL	Av ID (mm)	4.1	8.0	13.1	4.1	8.1	13.5	4.1	8.1	13.5	4.1	8.1	13.5
		CUC (%)	84.8	84.8	84.8	84.8	84.8	84.8	84.7	84.8	84.8	84.2	84.3	84.5

832 Figure 1

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839 Figure 2. Measured and manufacturer provided relationships between percent
840 timer setting (PTS, %) and irrigation time (hours). Simulated and manufacturer
841 provided relationships between PTS and applied irrigation depth (ID, mm).

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Figure 3. Relative frequency distribution of tower travel speed (only during the movement part of the cycles) for four irrigation events performed at different PTS (75%, 50%, 40% and 25 %).

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870 Figure 4. Relative frequency distribution of switching angles controlling tower
 871 movement (left side figures) and tower stop (right side figures) for the three
 872 inner towers and for four irrigation events performed at different PTS (75%,
 873 50%, 40% and 25 %).

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877 Figure 5. Comparison between measured and simulated absolute frequency of
 878 the on-times (left figures) and off-times (right figures) for each pivot tower for a
 879 part-circle (180°) irrigation event performed at 40% PTS.

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Figure 6. Comparison between measured and simulated absolute frequency of the on-times (left figures) and off-times (right figures) for each pivot tower and for a part-circle (180°) irrigation event performed at 75% PTS.

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Figure 7. Comparison between measured and simulated irrigation depth (mm) and Heermann and Hein uniformity coefficient (CU_{HH}, %), left and right figures, respectively; for the evaluated irrigation events. Dashed lines in the figures represent the 1:1 line.

915 Figure 8. Simulated radial, circular and total uniformities and its variability for
 916 five tower alignment qualities (complete aligned, current dynamics, a
 917 misalignment of 5°, 10° and 15°) and three wind speed conditions (1.1 m s-1, 3.3
 918 m s-1 and 4.7 m s-1) for the commercial center-pivot traveling at 100% PTS.

921 Figure 9. Simulated water distribution pattern (mm) of the center-pivot travelling complete aligned (Complete, figure a), at a
922 misalignment of 5° (A 5° , figure b) and at its maximum tower misalignment (A 15° , figure c) at 100% PTS and at a wind speed of 3.3
923 m s⁻¹.
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